

Title: Satellite observations and models informing agriculture: Training for Open Science under climate change

K. Arthur Endsley, Principal Investigator (PI)

Molly Brown, Co-Investigator (Co-I)

Walid Ouaret, Co-Investigator (Co-I)

Mourad Latati, Collaborator

Mohsen Nabil, Collaborator

**To be replaced with standard NASA Proposal Cover Page
(generated in NSPIRES)**

Proposal Summary

Projections of global climate change indicate that many agricultural regions will be warmer and drier. Elsewhere, intensification of the hydrological cycle may mean that rainfall is too intense, or less predictable, threatening established crop cycles and crop production. The study of these changes in the earth system is one of the goals of NASA's Science Mission Directorate (SMD), but the increasing reliance on computer-aided inference, including computational models and big datasets, requires skills that are neither thoroughly nor equitably distributed among domain scientists. Already, early-career climate scientists are spending too much professional time trying to solve frustrating issues of data access and software compatibility.

Effective, evidence-based decision making in agriculture and agronomy under a changing climate will require input from scientists that can combine models with large and diverse datasets, collaborating across open digital infrastructures. The reality is that the vast majority of domain scientists are self-taught when it comes to computer-aided inference and digital workflows. They lack the habits and best practices that are essential to identifying, acquiring, and analyzing NASA SMD datasets while ensuring reproducible and open results. This is especially problematic in less industrialized nations, where digital infrastructure is thin and training opportunities scarce.

We are a group of climate scientists, agronomists, and ecologists that have first-hand experience both teaching and learning how to use the tools and techniques of Open Science. We propose to develop a curriculum, **“Satellite Data and Models for Open Science in Agricultural Systems,”** to inculcate *Sustainable* Open Science in research settings. Our curriculum will cover the fundamentals of how climate datasets are produced and how prevailing climate and climate anomalies can be analyzed using NASA SMD datasets. Then, we will introduce the fundamental components of agricultural systems as subsequent modules: Water Resources, Healthy Soils, and Crops. Each module explores how NASA SMD data, especially cloud-ready datasets, can be used to answer specific, applied questions related to food security in the Middle East and Northern Africa (MENA) region. Specifically, NASA's investments including the Earth Observing System, Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP), the Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment (GRACE), and ECOSTRESS will demonstrate their value for analyzing agricultural water availability, soil health, crop condition, and production.

The five (5) ScienceCore modules we will develop as part of our curriculum will be based entirely in open-source software, implemented in Python, and distributed using literate programming tools like Jupyter Notebooks. We will make connections with NASA's OpenCore, filling in what we perceive to be gaps that learners frequently struggle with when first learning a programming workflow: how to manage large and diverse datasets; developing an explicable and reproducible workflow; separating algorithmic code from runtime parameters; documenting code; and how to verify algorithms or procedures.

The MENA region shares similarities with many semi-arid food-producing regions of the world, including the western United States, and both regions will feature as case studies. Open

Science means that science should be accessible, legible, and freely available irrespective of geography or location; therefore, our proposal team, which includes scientists from the MENA region, will translate lesson materials into French and Arabic to make sure this curriculum is ready for immediate adoption in the Francophone Mediterranean, Sub-Saharan Africa, and the MENA region. Our project will also deploy the curriculum for the first time, over two workshops, at the **École Nationale Supérieure Agronomique** in Algeria where students and researchers are excited to learn, maintain, and re-teach Sustainable Open Science.

Table of Contents

1	Scientific/ Technical/ Management Plan	1
1.1	Objectives and Expected Significance	1
1.1.1	Objectives	2
1.1.2	Expected Significance.....	2
1.1.3	Relevance to NASA and TOPS Training Solicitation	3
1.2	Curriculum Development Plan.....	3
1.2.1	Computational Data Science Skill-Building	6
1.2.2	NASA Datasets Used.....	8
1.3	Dissemination and Broader Impacts	9
1.4	Work Plan and Key Milestones.....	9
1.5	Redacted Budget and Budget Narrative	10
2	References and Citations.....	11
3	Open Source Science Development Plan.....	12
3.1	Software Management Plan.....	12
3.2	Data Management Plan.....	12
4	Expertise and Resources - Not Anonymized	14
4.1	Biographical Sketches	14
4.2	Contributions of Key Personnel	19
4.3	Current and Pending Support	20
4.4	Budget Details and Justification.....	21
4.4.1	Budget Narrative.....	21
4.4.2	Budget Details: University of Montana NTSG.....	22
4.5	Summary Table of Work Effort	26
4.6	Facilities and Equipment	27
4.7	Letters of Support.....	29

1 Scientific/ Technical/ Management Plan

1.1 Objectives and Expected Significance

Of the many expected impacts of climate change on human societies, the consequences for agriculture and food security are perhaps the most dire, particularly for populations in less industrialized and more arid regions, such as the Middle East and North Africa (MENA). The approaches used to study and anticipate these impacts are driven by climate data, yet many agronomists, soil scientists, and other researchers lack the computational training to make effective use of downscaled climate projections, re-analysis datasets, or satellite remote sensing data (Figure 1). At the same time, climate data volumes are steadily increasing; the latest Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP), CMIP6, produced an estimated 20-40 petabytes of data [1]. Despite the utility and prevalence of these model outputs, **the vast majority of domain scientists who use computer-generated datasets and algorithms are self-taught** [2]. Climate scientists have voiced concern that an increasing amount of their professional time is being spent on “downloading and transferring data, debugging codes, and solving compatibility issues between software libraries” [1], which suggests that improvements in both computational tools and training are essential for advancing earth system science [3–5]. Effective training in computer-aided inference should, therefore, emphasize high-level tools that leverage cloud-based datasets designed for interoperability as well as the data and workflow management techniques that enable *tractable and reproducible* data processing pipelines.

Figure 1: There are many challenges to conducting Open Science in agricultural systems, especially in the Middle East and North Africa. Computational data science skills (SK1-5) can help (Section 1.2.2). *Photo from Africa Freedom Network.*

Researchers in the MENA region and in developing nations face unique barriers in addition to these disciplinary challenges [6]. Other than Israel and Tunisia, none of the MENA nations are above the 25th percentile for Open Science policies and practices, according to the Global Open Data Barometer [7], which may reflect histories of unequal trans-national

partnerships and of data expropriation by investigators from high-income countries. There is also a wide divergence in the technological capabilities and digital infrastructures of nations in this region [8]. Digital storage constraints and too-frequent power and internet connectivity outages [1, 9] point to the benefit of cloud-based tools and datasets that make fewer assumptions about computing capacity or availability. And yet, the use of cloud-based solutions requires training beyond most climate-science or agronomy educational programs, even in high-income countries. **NASA’s definition of Open Science might be extended to explicitly include making science accessible, legible, and freely available irrespective of geography or location.**

1.1.1 Objectives

NASA’s OpenCore curriculum is highly relevant for researchers in the MENA region and in the Global South more broadly, as much of the capacity-building that is needed involves the development and adoption of open data networks and repositories [6, 10]. **We propose to develop a curriculum that extends OpenCore with training in cutting-edge data-science skills, presented through agricultural and climate science applications.** These applications will leverage NASA’s Science Mission Directorate (SMD) investments in satellite-based observations and modeling and inspire domain scientists whose work is relevant to NASA’s Earth Science Division. **Therefore, this curriculum is centered in three topic areas relevant to climate and agriculture: Water Resources, Healthy Soils, and Crops.** The goal of this curriculum is to prepare scientists studying climate and/or agriculture to be more productive, to utilize NASA SMD datasets in studying short-term effects and long-term projections of agriculture under climate change, and to effectively document and make reproducible their computer-aided inference—these are elements of *Sustainable Open Science* in agriculture and climate studies. **Our four objectives are:**

- **Objective 1 (Obj1):** Develop a Python-based ScienceCore curriculum, **“Satellite Data and Models for Open Science in Agricultural Systems.”** that teaches essential skills and best practices in reproducible, computer-aided analysis of NASA SMD datasets.
- **Objective 2 (Obj2):** Deploy the curriculum in an online, collaborative environment and solicit feedback from Open Science, scientific Python, and domain science communities.
- **Objective 3 (Obj3):** Translate all lesson materials into the dominant MENA languages (French and Arabic).
- **Objective 4 (Obj4):** Host at least one in-person workshop where the curriculum is taught in the MENA region and train collaborators there to teach and maintain the curriculum.

1.1.2 Expected Significance

To leverage NASA’s valuable investments in observational and modeled datasets, scientists must develop *computational proficiency*, which includes data literacy, data science, and software project management [3]. Our proposed curriculum includes learning objectives identified by the Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics (SIAM) as essential for graduate programs in computational science and engineering [4]: Awareness “of available tools and techniques...their

strengths, and their weaknesses;” “Develop, select, and use tools and methods to represent and visualize computational results;” and “Identify the sources of error” in computer-generated data products “and understand how to diagnose them and work to reduce or eliminate them.” By extending NASA’s *OpenCore* curriculum with training in data management, workflow management, version control, and verification, our curriculum also responds to the need, identified by SIAM, for training in “**software sustainability**,” which overlaps with the goals of NASA’s commitment to open science. Software sustainability includes, at its core, **reproducibility**, which is an important standard for computational inference [11], and we propose to teach reproducibility through best practices. **By translating our curriculum in its entirety into French and Arabic, we will directly address the widely-cited language barriers that have inhibited the adoption of Open Science in Africa and the MENA region [6].**

1.1.3 Relevance to NASA and TOPS Training Solicitation

Our curriculum aims to empower earth scientists working in agricultural systems with the best tools and techniques in computational data science, in order to “understand the Earth System and its climate” (NASA FY22 Strategic Goal 1.1), to make science data “accessible to all” (Goal 1.3), and to “develop a talented and diverse workforce” (Goal 4.1). It emphasizes both efficiency and reproducibility, which are key to innovation and entrepreneurship (NASA SMD Science Plan, Strategy 2.1) as well as fostering collaboration (Strategy 2.2). We are leveraging the opportunity to develop this curriculum in partnership with collaborators from Algeria and Egypt, countries confronted with warming and drying trends but under-resourced for Open Science. As a demonstration of our project’s value, **we will travel to and teach the curriculum at École Nationale Supérieure Agronomique (ENSA) in Algiers, Algeria over the course of two annual workshops.** Hence, our proposal explicitly advances the Science Plan’s Strategy 3.2.

In developing a curriculum that targets a diverse, international audience, our project contributes directly to the NASA SMD Science Plan’s goal to “increase the diversity of thought and backgrounds represented across the entire SMD portfolio” (Strategy 4.1). In teaching the curriculum, our efforts to combat stereotype threat, to empower learners with hands-on and peer programming techniques, and to disseminate our curriculum to in-country instructors through capacity-building are also conducive to building an “inclusive environment” (Strategy 4.1) for earth science education. **Furthermore, our curriculum addresses NASA’s commitment to equity and inclusion in three specific areas:** Lesson materials will be available in multiple languages; only free and open-source software is introduced; and instruction on data visualization explicitly considers the needs of colorblind and visually impaired learners.

1.2 Curriculum Development Plan

Our proposal team is unique in that it consists of both subject-matter experts and novices; teachers and students. In developing an effective, hands-on, applied science curriculum, we will benefit from the recent experience of those who learned (and perhaps struggled with) the material for the first time. We are domain scientists, not computer scientists, just like our target

audience. And yet, our curriculum’s learning objectives emphasize the skills and concepts that are regularly used by computer modelers and programmers: **Abstraction, Decomposition, Algorithmic thinking, and Continuous integration** [12, 13].

The overarching goal of the curriculum, **“Satellite Data and Models for Open Science in Agricultural Systems,”** is to inculcate *Sustainable Open Science* practices among scientists working with NASA SMD datasets (Obj1). To that end, our curriculum blends domain science with best practices in data science (Table 1). The latter reflect essential data-science skills (Section 1.2.1) that generalize beyond climate and agricultural studies. Learners do not acquire these skills by rote or lecture but through practice with real-world applications. **Hence, the curriculum is oriented around climate data applications (M1, M2) and the key elements of the agricultural systems: Water Resources (M3), Healthy Soils (M4), and Crops (M5).** Each module introduces a climate-science or agricultural science workflow and includes *learning outcomes* (Table 1) relevant to NASA SMD’s Earth Science Division. A *learning outcome* describes what a learner is expected to achieve as a result of a learning activity [4] and is often described in terms of the learner’s resulting capabilities.

The capabilities developed over the course of the five modules are cumulative; i.e., subsequent modules build on previous capabilities. **The modules are linked by a narrative that we will develop around a region of interest and each module asks and answers different questions about this region’s agricultural system(s):** What climate regimes currently prevail? (M1); What climate variability negatively impacts crops? (M2); What water resources are available? (M3); How does soil health vary across the landscape? (M4); How much water do crops demand? (M5). As learners address these questions, they will develop two parallel file systems, one for input datasets and derived results, while the other is for science code.

Module 1 (M1), “Open Climate Data,” builds the foundation of the curriculum by empowering learners to access Earth observation datasets, open them in Jupyter Notebook, and perform a basic analysis of multi-dimensional gridded climate data. M1 introduces learners to NASA EarthData Search as a means of indexing and accessing climate datasets. Learners begin to organize their workspace for effective, data-intensive analyses: the module’s goal (reading and plotting climate data) is decomposed into successive tasks; project scripts (Jupyter Notebooks) are named effectively and grouped according to tasks; the processing pipeline is introduced, whereby raw data are preserved, separate “clean” datasets are produced, and results can be

Figure 2: Our curriculum consists of 5 thematic modules.

reproduced. Throughout this module, we motivate the idea of *scientific provenance*, i.e., the full accounting of how scientific results are obtained. Accessibility is emphasized in a discussion of making plots that are legible and choosing color scales that are perceptually linear and accessible for colorblind viewers. This module introduces NASA SMD datasets on long-term average temperatures, air saturation, and precipitation (**MERRA-2**, see **Section 1.2.2**) as well as near-real time data on precipitation rate and totals (**IMERG**).

Module 2 (M2), “Scientific Programming for Climate Studies,” equips learners with concrete skills for computer-aided inference about agricultural systems under climate change. Concepts like machine precision, testing and assertions, and vectorization may seem the province exclusively of computer science but, in fact, are extremely important for building satellite-data processing pipelines, simulating water and carbon fluxes, or modeling crop condition and performance. As such, the skills introduced in this module are reinforced in subsequent modules as learners develop more sophisticated Python scripts and functions. The module culminates in the calculation of a drought index, which is established based on a soil moisture *climatology* and weekly soil moisture *anomalies*, two domain concepts introduced in the module. Soil moisture (**SMAP L4SM**) and canopy greenness (**MODIS, Landsat**) datasets are introduced.

Module 3 (M3), “Open Science for Water Resources,” introduces source control management (SCM), initially as a means of backing-up their code, and ultimately as a means of collaboration on GitHub: filing issues to track development progress, linking comments to specific lines in source code, and looking at changesets. Learners review an example science code repository on GitHub and are asked to create their own repository based on that example with the code they produced in this module. M3 culminates with the learner calculating a simple water budget at catchment scale, once learners have been introduced to the types of water resources data available from NASA SMD assets and missions: rainfall rate and totals (**IMERG**), water storage anomalies (**GRACE**), and evapotranspiration (ET) (**MODIS MOD16**). The pipeline they develop for this purpose will be based on runtime input parameter (RIP) files, a technique for separating the logic of a general-purpose processing pipeline from the specific configuration used. We discuss how RIP files help establish *scientific provenance* by explicitly documenting datasets that were inputs to the pipeline, any configurable parameters, as well as the name(s) and location(s) of output files.

Module 4 (M4), “Open Science for Soil Health,” focuses on mapping soil dynamic properties associated with soil health and, ultimately, health and productive crops. Mapping these properties is typically performed through the classification of remotely sensed imagery (**Landsat**) and other spatially explicit data on terrestrial surface conditions [14, 15], though mechanistic models are also used [16]. We introduce learners to both kinds, including NASA SMD datasets (**SMAP L4C**), and they practice scientific programming skills (SK4) developed in the previous module by building a soil health classification pipeline. We use this pipeline as a framing for two important scientific programming skills: resource profiling and modularization. Most domain scientists are implementing scientific pipelines on desktop hardware and are unaware, or unconcerned, with their code’s performance [17]. While the accuracy of the code is

the foremost concern, severe bottlenecks can negatively impact science results by discouraging comprehensive searches of a parameter space or encouraging non-representative data subsetting. Similarly, modularization can help programmers be more efficient and avoid mistakes. A soil health classification pipeline is an ideal example because it is CPU-bound and learners will quickly discover they need to be strategic in how the training data are prepared.

Module 5 (M5), “Open Science for Crop Conditions and Crop Production,” brings into focus the final element of agricultural systems: plants. Here, learners are introduced to multiple NASA SMD datasets for monitoring crop conditions based on departure from average conditions: gross primary productivity (GPP) from **SMAP L4C** and both ET and the evaporative stress index from **ECOSTRESS** (see **Section 1.2.2**). M5 culminates in the calculation of the Water Requirement Satisfaction Index (WRSI), a budget-based accounting of crop-available water similar to the calculation performed in M3. We leverage the WRSI as an example of a model implementation, motivating questions about model verification (i.e., is the model correctly implemented?), testing (how can we ensure the model’s logic is unchanged when we refactor the code?), and deployment (how can others reproduce our computational results?). Thus, the final module engages learners to consider the full stakes of *Sustainable Open Science*.

1.2.1 Computational Data Science Skill-Building

While each module is focused on a topical theme, there are also five data science skills that will be emphasized throughout the curriculum:

- **SK1, Project and Data Management:** Separation of raw data from processed or derived datasets; Organization of a project’s file system; Open collaboration tools.
- **SK2, Science Communication:** Scientific provenance; Literate programming and tools (Jupyter Notebooks); Data visualization and designing for color-blindness.
- **SK3, Source Control Management:** Understanding source control management; Motivation for version control; Introduction to Git and GitHub; Best practices for collaborating under version control; Semantic versioning; Continuous integration.
- **SK4, Scientific Programming:** Testing and assertions; Machine representation of numbers; Reading/ writing hierarchical datasets (HDF5, netCDF4) and spatial datasets; Vectorization; Concurrency; Resource profiling.
- **SK5, Sustainable Scientific Software Development:** Reproducibility; Data processing pipelines; Code and model verification; Separation of code and data; Runtime-input parameter files; Modularization and code re-use; Deployment.

Each thematic module will introduce one or more skills and later modules cumulatively build upon these skills. **The skills reflect well-established best practices in scientific computing [2, 18], emphasizing how adherence to these practices can make the individual learner more efficient and productive in their research while avoiding time-consuming mistakes.** In addition, our lesson materials require learners to engage with core, open-source Python libraries: GDAL, NumPy, SciPy, h5py, netCDF4, rasterio, scikit-learn, and scikit-image.

Table 1: Outline of the proposed curriculum, “Satellite Data and Models for Open Science in Agricultural Systems,” and learning objectives. The column “Data-Science Learning Outcomes” and colors refer to the data science skills identified in Section 1.2.1.

Module	Domain-Science Learning Outcomes	Data-Science Learning Outcomes
<p>M1: Open Climate Data</p> <p><i>How are NASA satellites, field data, and models used to diagnose and predict Earth’s climate system? How is climate variability measured and modeled?</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand how the estimates of reanalysis datasets, General Circulation Models, and Earth System Models are generated; how they differ. • Know where different climate variables (e.g., precipitation, temperature) can be obtained at the appropriate spatial and temporal scales. • Demonstrate the use of multiple climate variables from different climate datasets. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data hygiene: Separating raw data from derivatives (SK1) • Project management: Decomposing a science goal into tasks; Organizing a file system around those tasks (SK1) • Literate programming: Use of Jupyter Notebooks; Narrate and document scientific workflows (SK2) • Data visualization: Selecting perceptually linear color scales (SK2)
<p>M2: Scientific Programming for Climate Studies</p> <p><i>How can we analyze gridded climate datasets with spatial and temporal attributes?</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe the interpretation and calculation of climate normals, climate anomalies, and a climatology. • Understand what indices are available for meteorological drought, soil moisture drought, atmospheric water demand, canopy greenness. • Culmination: Calculate a simple drought index based on precipitation anomalies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Machine precision: Accurately represent and compress numeric data (SK4) • Scientific datasets: Read and write HDF5, netCDF4, and spatial data files (SK4) • Vectorization: Apply custom functions at scale to numerical arrays (SK4) • Code verification: Know when and how to use testing and assertions (SK4)
<p>M3: Open Science for Water Resources</p> <p><i>What tools and datasets are available to quantify water quantity and availability?</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the major fluxes and pools of the terrestrial water cycle. • Know where to access remotely sensed or modeled data on water storage anomalies, evapotranspiration, and soil moisture. • Culmination: Calculate a water budget. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Source control management (SCM): Explain, justify, and use SCM (SK3) • Collaborative SCM (SK3): Understand collaboration options built into GitHub • Scientific provenance: Build workflows that are traceable (SK2) • Runtime input parameter files (SK5): Create metadata about scientific workflows

<p>M4: Open Science for Soil Health</p> <p><i>How can satellite observations and models help to predict and map indicators of soil health?</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know what remote-sensing and model-derived datasets are available to map dynamic soil properties (pH, SOC, soil texture). • Understand the basics of statistical learning and how classifiers are trained and validated against independent data • Culmination: Apply principal component analysis (PCA) and clustering to map soil categories, based on a soil spectra library. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documenting assumptions and potential biases: All models are biased (SK2) • Source control management (SCM): Explain and use Merging, Branching, and Pull Requests (SK3) • Resource profiling: Know how to evaluate the performance of science code (SK4) • Modularization: Understand when and how to separate functions into different namespaces (SK5)
<p>M5: Open Science for Crop Conditions and Crop Production</p> <p><i>How can NASA datasets be used to map crop conditions?</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access and utilize satellite-based datasets on plant productivity, condition, and evapotranspiration. • Understand how plants link between the carbon and water cycles through photosynthesis and evapotranspiration. • Culmination: Compute the Water Requirement Satisfaction Index (WRSI) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Source control management (SCM): Employ best practices for open-source repositories (SK3) • Deployment: Create open-source repositories that can be shared and re-used (SK5) • Code verification: Write code allowing verification of science/model logic (SK5)

1.2.2 NASA Datasets Used

Our curriculum leverages NASA’s investments both in satellite missions and in operational climate models, specifically:

- **MERRA-2 Re-analysis**, the NASA Global Modeling and Assimilation Office (GMAO) Modern-Era Retrospective analysis for Research and Applications (**Modules M1, M2**)
- **IMERG**, Integrated Multi-satellite Retrievals for GPM (Global Precipitation Measurement Mission) (**Modules M1, M3**)
- **MODIS**, Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer, MOD15 fPAR and MOD16 ET (**Modules M2, M3, M5**)
- **Landsat 8 and 9** visible, near-infrared, and short-wave infrared surface reflectance (**Modules M2, M4**)
- **SMAP L4SM**: Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) Level 4 Soil Moisture (L4SM) (**Modules M3, M4, M5**)
- **SMAP L4C**: SMAP Level 4 Carbon, including Gross Primary Productivity and Soil Organic Carbon (**Modules M4, M5**)
- **ECOSTRESS**, ECOsystem Spaceborne Thermal Radiometer Experiment on Space Station, Evaporative Stress Index (**M5**)
- **GRACE**, Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment WET Surface Mass Anomaly (**Module M3**)

1.3 Dissemination and Broader Impacts

We envision that the final curriculum will be taught for the first time, once each project year, at the École Nationale Supérieure Agronomique (ENSA) in Algiers, Algeria, which has graciously agreed to provide in-kind support for teaching activities, including travel funding for the PI. Co-I #2, who is fluent in French and Arabic, and Collaborator #1, located in Algiers, will assist with teaching and logistics. We expect to recruit local students and researchers to contribute to and maintain the curriculum so that it can continue to be taught locally in later years. The Year 1 workshop in Algeria will use a draft curriculum, which may be incomplete; this allows us to offer additional instruction on Python programming, preparing learners for Year 2.

In addition, Co-I #2 will facilitate the translation of lesson materials into French and Arabic, which are widely spoken throughout the MENA region, including Egypt, Morocco, and Tunisia. We anticipate that the translated materials will be very relevant for scientists throughout the Global South where one or both languages are also spoken, in parts of southeast Asia and especially in Africa: Benin, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Chad, the Republic of Congo, Gabon, the Ivory Coast, Niger, Senegal. While Co-I #2's French proficiency is sufficient for a complete translation of the lesson materials, assistance with written Arabic will be obtained through a translation service, coordinated by Co-I #2, who is fluent in spoken Arabic.

1.4 Work Plan and Key Milestones

Table 2: Summary Table of Work Effort with key activities indicated.

Member	Tasks and Responsibilities
PI	Year 1: Assembling example datasets; Writing module narrative; Teaching initial draft curriculum in Algeria; Year 2: Proofing final module contents; Teaching final draft curriculum in Algeria. Throughout: Developing module contents; Convening the CAC; Summarizing and reporting to NASA; Promoting the curriculum in open science communities.
Co-I #1	Year 1: Provide feedback on curriculum Storyboard; Throughout: Advising Co-I #2; Participating in the CAC.
Co-I #2	Year 1: Teaching initial draft curriculum in Algeria; Year 2: Translating curriculum in French; Supervising translation into Arabic; Teaching final draft curriculum in Algeria. Throughout: Testing modules; Developing module contents; Participating in the CAC.
Collaborator #1	Years 1 and 2: Assisting with on-site teaching in Algeria; Throughout: Participating in the CAC.
Collaborator #2	Throughout: Participating in the CAC.

The development of this curriculum is proposed to take place over two years. In each year, the Curriculum Advisory Committee (CAC) will meet at least four times (once per quarter). The CAC is comprised of all team members but Co-I #1 and Collaborators #1 and #2 have special prominence as domain experts in agricultural systems, soil science, and remote sensing, respectively. PI will convene and set the agenda for the CAC; this is expected to include a focus on one or two modules, solicitation from domain experts, and the evaluation of learning

outcomes. Co-I #1 will be responsible for supervising Co-I #2, who is a doctoral student, insofar as what is required for the student to remain in good standing. Co-I #1 will also participate in the CAC, advising on curriculum content and narrative, and promote the curriculum. Both Collaborators are based in the MENA region and experts in studying agricultural systems.

The **Key Milestones** in each year are:

- **Year 1 Milestone:** Develop a curriculum Storyboard that completely describes the steps in each Lesson Plan, the datasets used, and the learning outcomes (**Obj1**).
- **Year 1 Milestone:** Teach initial draft curriculum at ENSA in Algeria (**Obj3, Obj4**).
- **Year 2 Milestone:** Complete final draft of the curriculum and publish it on an open platform (**Obj1, Obj2**); solicit feedback from user communities.
- **Year 2 Milestone:** Teach the draft curriculum at ENSA in Algeria (**Obj3, Obj4**).

1.5 Redacted Budget and Budget Narrative

Direct costs include salary (PI salary not shown below), domestic travel, consultant services (for Arabic translation), and a sub-award to the second institution of the proposal team. The PI is requesting support for 3 months per year. Domestic travel costs are to support the PI to travel to the American Geophysical Union Fall Meeting conference in Year 2 (expected 2024) in order to promote the initial draft curriculum; the cost includes registration (\$600), airfare (estimated \$700), meals per diem (\$216), and lodging with tax included (estimated \$1,268). Foreign travel costs for the PI are covered by ENSA (see Letter of Support). Direct costs also include the sub-award, which includes salary for Co-Is, equipment (a high-powered computer for Co-I #2), open-access publication costs (once per project year), computing services (computing support at Institution #2), and foreign travel for Co-I #2 to Algeria in Years 1 and 2. Foreign travel costs for Co-I #2 are the same in both years and include a hotel (4 nights, \$580 total), per diem (\$305 total), airfare (estimated \$2,000), and incidentals (\$115).

	Year 1	Year 2	Total Project
A. PI Effort (# months)	3.0	3.0	6.0
B. Domestic Travel		\$2,784	\$2,784
C. Other Direct Costs:	\$105,986	\$86,349	\$199,835
1. Consultant Services (Translation)		\$7,500	\$7,500
2. Sub-award	\$105,986	\$86,349	\$192,335
D. Direct Costs (B through C)	\$105,986	\$96,663	\$202,619

2 References and Citations

1. Jain S, Mindlin J, Koren G, Gulizia C, Steadman C, Langendijk GS, Osman M, Abid MA, Rao Y, Rabanal V (2022) Are We at Risk of Losing the Current Generation of Climate Researchers to Data Science? *AGU Advances*. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022AV000676>
2. Wilson G, Aruliah D, Brown CT, et al (2014) Best Practices for Scientific Computing. *PLoS Biology*. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1001745>
3. Heroux MA, Allen G (2016) Computational Science And Engineering Software Sustainability And Productivity (CSESSP) Challenges Workshop Report. Networking and Information Technology Research and Development (NITRD) Program
4. Rüde U, Willcox K, McInnes LC, Sterck HD (2018) Research and Education in Computational Science and Engineering. *SIAM Rev* 60:707–754
5. Rodríguez-Sánchez F, Marwick B, Lazowska E, VanderPlas J (2017) Academia’s failure to retain data scientists. *Science* 355:357–358
6. Fox M, Hanlon SM (2015) Barriers to Open Access uptake for researchers in Africa. *Online Information Review* 39:698–716
7. World Wide Web Foundation The Open Data Barometer. https://opendatabarometer.org/4thedition/?_year=2016&indicator=ODB®ion=:ME. Accessed 7 Nov 2022
8. Mwelwa J, Boulton G, Wafula JM, Loucoubar C (2020) Developing Open Science in Africa: Barriers, Solutions and Opportunities. *CODATA* 19:31
9. Ahinon J, Havemann J (2018) Open Science in Africa - Challenges, Opportunities and Perspectives. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.1492745>
10. Boulton G, Loucoubar C, Mwelwa J, Wafula M (2020) The Digital Revolution, Open Science and Innovation for Development in Sub-Saharan Africa. 12
11. Stodden V, McNutt M, Bailey DH, Deelman E, Gil Y, Hanson B, Heroux MA, Ioannidis JPA, Taufer M (2016) Enhancing reproducibility for computational methods. *Science* 354:1240–1241
12. Shute VJ, Sun C, Asbell-Clarke J (2017) Demystifying computational thinking. *Educational Research Review* 22:142–158
13. Wing JM (2006) Computational thinking. *Commun ACM* 49:33–35
14. Demattê JAM, Fongaro CT, Rizzo R, Safanelli JL (2018) Geospatial Soil Sensing System (GEOS3): A powerful data mining procedure to retrieve soil spectral reflectance from satellite images. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 212:161–175
15. Ward KJ, Chabrilat S, Neumann C, Foerster S (2019) A remote sensing adapted approach for soil organic carbon prediction based on the spectrally clustered LUCAS soil database. *Geoderma* 353:297–307
16. Endsley KA, Kimball JS, Reichle RH, Watts JD (2020) Satellite monitoring of global surface soil organic carbon dynamics using the SMAP Level 4 Carbon Product. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Biogeosciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020JG006100>
17. Prabhu P, Zhang Y, Ghosh S, et al (2011) A survey of the practice of computational science. In: *State of the Practice Reports on - SC '11*. ACM Press, Seattle, Washington, p 1
18. Lapp Z, Sovacool K, Lesniak N, et al (2022) Developing and deploying an integrated workshop curriculum teaching computational skills for reproducible research. *JOSE* 5:144

3 Open Source Science Development Plan

Our curriculum will be developed under source control management using Git and a public GitHub repository. This will enable us to promote the curriculum, track progress with the Curriculum Advisory Committee, and solicit feedback from the wider community at an early stage. At the end of the project, all software (lesson materials) will be archived at code.nasa.gov, if possible, while the GitHub repository will persist (and grow) indefinitely. Any custom datasets produced for the curriculum will be archived on Zenodo.org. Both software and the final curriculum's data archive will receive unique digital object identifiers (DOIs). Outcomes for project software and data are described in more detail below.

3.1 Software Management Plan

All project software will be under source control management with a public, peer repository on GitHub. The PI will coordinate and provide any necessary training for project members in the use of Git and GitHub. Unless otherwise directed by NASA, we will choose the MIT License for all project code, given its wide use and permissivity that does not exclude educational uses that may be considered for-profit. We will also explore a hosted Jupyter Hub instance that will both: 1) Allow for project team members to collaboratively view and interact with Python lesson materials; 2) Allow learners in Algeria as well as the wider community to quickly preview and evaluate module contents.

To further elicit feedback and interest from the scientific computing community, Modules M1 and M2 will be cross-posted to the Carpentries Incubator, a program that encourages the collaborative development of lesson materials. These modules form a foundation for preparing learners to use Python for scientific programming in climate-related studies. Promotion on the Carpentries Incubator will help to grow the audience for the complete curriculum and generate interest in NASA and the TOPS program. This may require porting M1 and M2 to a separate repository, to follow best practices for the Incubator, but that repository will also be public, on GitHub, and will be explicitly linked to the original project GitHub repository.

If scripts or software tools are developed by the project team to help advance curriculum development but are not themselves a part of any lesson materials, that software shall also be made available in the same public GitHub repository, separate from lesson materials. Lesson materials will use only free and open-source Python software libraries; learners will not be asked to install any proprietary or fee-based software. The core open-source Python libraries we plan to teach include: GDAL, NumPy, SciPy, h5py, netCDF4, rasterio, scikit-learn, and scikit-image.

3.2 Data Management Plan

We will prioritize the use of cloud-ready datasets from NASA EarthData for all lesson materials. Where necessary, we will prepare subsets of datasets for learners to use. Data used in the curriculum, whether cloud-based or customized, will only be based on publicly available datasets; the vast majority will be accessible through NASA EarthData Search. The entire

process for creating derivative datasets will be documented and code and metadata made available in the same repository (see Software Management Plan, above). The derivative data themselves will initially be hosted and publicly available on a Secure FTP site controlled by Institution #1 and the PI, which will balance the needs for rapid development and open access. The PI and Co-I #2 will work together to select, manage, and archive any customized datasets, based on feedback from the Curriculum Advisory Committee. Before the end of the project, any derivative data will be archived with a DOI at Zenodo.org. Derivative datasets will be formatted as either GeoTIFF or Hierarchical Data Format Version 5 (HDF5) files.

4 Expertise and Resources - Not Anonymized

4.1 Biographical Sketches

(On following pages.)

K. Arthur Endsley (Principal Investigator)
Numerical Terradynamic Simulation Group (NTSG)
W.A. Franke College of Forestry & Conservation
Interdisciplinary Sciences Bldg. 416, University of Montana, Missoula MT 59812
Email: arthur.endsley@ntsg.umt.edu

Relevant experience:

Taught workshops on computational data science in Python and R at the Federal Reserve Board in Washington D.C., the Aspen Global Change Institute, West Virginia University, Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, and NASA Langley. Serves as the lead technical expert for maintenance, calibration, and re-processing of the NASA Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) Level 4 Carbon (L4C) product. Teaches modeling and programming in the Systems Ecology and Geography programs at the University of Montana.

Education

Ph.D. (2019) University of Michigan Natural Resources and Scientific Computing
B.S. (2009) Michigan Technological University Applied Geophysics

Appointments

2019-Present Research Scientist, College of Forestry and Conservation, University of Montana
2017-2019 Doctoral Fellow, Graham Sustainability Institute, University of Michigan
2014-2019 Graduate Student Research Assistant, School for Environment and Sustainability, University of Michigan
2012-2014 Research Scientist I, Michigan Tech Research Inst., Michigan Technological Univ.
2010-2011 Assistant Research Scientist, Michigan Tech Research Institute, Michigan Technological University

(i) Selected Publications/ Products Related to the Proposed Research

Endsley, K.A., J.S. Kimball, R.H. Reichle, and J.D. Watts, 2020. Satellite monitoring of global surface soil organic carbon dynamics using the SMAP Level 4 Carbon product. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Biogeosciences*, 125(12).

Endsley, K.A., M.G. Billmire. 2016. "Distributed visualization of gridded geophysical data: the Carbon Data Explorer, version 0.2.3" *Geoscientific Model Development* 9:383-392.

Endsley, K.A. and J.L. McCarty. 2013. "Mapping prescribed burns and wildfires from Twitter with natural language processing and information retrieval techniques." In *Proceedings of the International Smoke Symposium*. Hyattsville, Maryland, U.S.A. Wurster, P., M.P. Maneta, J.S. Kimball, **K.A. Endsley**, S. Beguería. 2020. Monitoring crop status in the Continental United States using the SMAP Level 4 Carbon product. *Frontiers in Big Data*.

Osenga, E.C., J.C. Arnott, **K.A. Endsley**, J. Katzenberger. 2019. "Bioclimatic and soil moisture monitoring across elevation in a mountain watershed: Opportunities for research and resource management." *Water Resources Research* 55(3): 2493-2503.

(ii) Software and Datasets Produced:

K.A. Endsley. 2021. suntransit (v0.1.0): Simple, fast approximation of sunrise, sunset time on Earth. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5555109

K.A. Endsley. 2021. simsoil: Very simple, point-scale soil hydrology model (Version 0.1.0). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4906830

K.A. Endsley. 2021. pyl4c: Tools for working with SMAP L4C and Terrestrial Carbon Flux (TCF) Model data (Version 0.12.0.dev). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5156231

Endsley, K.A. 2019. The unmixing library: Interactive tools for spectral mixture analysis of multispectral raster data in Python v0.2.4.dev. Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/record/3585979>

Kimball, J. S., L. A. Jones, **A. Endsley**, T. Kundig, and R. Reichle. 2021. SMAP L4 Global Daily 9 km EASE-Grid Carbon Net Ecosystem Exchange, Version 6. Boulder, Colorado USA. NASA National Snow and Ice Data Center Distributed Active Archive Center.

Kimball, J.S., L.A. Jones, **K.A. Endsley**, T. Kundig, and R. Reichle. 2020. SMAP L4 Global Daily 9 km EASE-Grid Carbon Net Ecosystem Exchange, Version 5. Boulder, Colorado USA. NASA National Snow and Ice Data Center Distributed Active Archive Center.

(iii) Other Significant Products:

Endsley, K.A., J.S. Kimball, R.H. Reichle. 2022. "Soil respiration phenology improves modeled phase of terrestrial net ecosystem exchange in northern hemisphere." *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems* **14**(2).

Endsley, K.A., D.G. Brown, E. Bruch. 2018. "Housing market activity is associated with disparities in urban and metropolitan vegetation." *Ecosystems*.

N. Madani, N.C. Parazoo, J.S. Kimball, R.H. Reichle, A. Chatterjee, J.D. Watts, S. Saatchi, Z. Liu, **K.A. Endsley**, T. Tagesson, B.M. Rogers, A. Xu, J.A. Wang, T. Magney, C.E. Miller. 2021. "The impacts of climate and wildfire on ecosystem gross primary productivity in Alaska." *Journal of Geophysical Research: Biogeosciences* **126**(6).

Miller, M.E., W.J. Elliot, M. Billmire, P.R. Robichaud, **K.A. Endsley**. 2016. "Rapid-response tools and datasets for post-fire remediation: linking remote sensing and process-based hydrological models." *International Journal of Wildland Fire* **25**, 1061-1073.

Gonzalez, A., B.J. Cardinale, G.R.H. Allington, J. Byrnes, **K.A. Endsley**, D.G. Brown, D.U. Hooper, F. Isbell, M. Loreaue, M.I. O'Connor. 2016. "Estimating local biodiversity change: A critique of papers claiming no net loss of local diversity." *Ecology* **97**(8): 1949–1960.

Josberger, E.G., R.A. Shuchman, L.K. Jenkins, and **K.A. Endsley**. 2014. "Melt water input from the Bering Glacier Watershed into the Gulf of Alaska." *Geophysical Research Letters*. **41**(3): 886-890

French N.H.F., D. McKenzie, T. Erickson, B. Koziol, M. Billmire, **K.A. Endsley**, N.K.Y. Scheinerman, L. Jenkins, M.E. Miller, R. Ottmar, S. Prichard. 2014. "Modeling regional-scale fire emissions with the Wildland Fire Emissions Information System." *Earth Interactions* **18**(16).

Andrus, A.B., **K.A. Endsley**, S. Espino, J.S. Gierke. 2010. Mapping the Freshwater-Saltwater Interface in the Terminal Moraine of the Bering Glacier. Ch. 19. Bering Glacier: Interdisciplinary Studies of Earth's Largest Temperate Surging Glacier. Special Paper 462. Geological Society of America.

(iv) Teaching & Curriculum Development:

“Programming for GIS” (Spring 2023), University of Montana, Missoula, MT

“Integrated Systems Ecology” (Spring 2022), University of Montana, Missoula, MT

“Natural Resource Statistics” (Fall 2018), University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, MI

“Urban Sustainability” (Fall 2016), University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, MI

Molly E. Brown, PhD

Department of Geographical Sciences
University of Maryland
College Park, MD 20171

mbrown52@umd.edu
703-855-6190 (c)

EDUCATION

Ph.D. in Geography, University of Maryland College Park, 2002
M.A. in Geography, University of Maryland College Park, 1998
B.S. in Biology and Environmental Sciences, Tufts University, 1991

EMPLOYMENT HISTORY

Research Associate Professor, Department of Geographical Sciences, University of Maryland	2/15 - present
Research Scientist, NASA Goddard Space Flight Center	10/08 – 1/15
Senior Research Scientist, Science Systems and Applications, Inc. at NASA	3/02 – 9/08
Faculty Research Assistant, University of Maryland	1/99 – 3/02
Professional Education Program Manager, SENECA	7/94 – 9/95
Volunteer, US Peace Corps, Senegal	6/92 – 7/94

RELEVANT JOURNAL PUBLICATIONS

- M.E. Brown**, K. Grace, T. Billing and D. Backer (2021) Considering climate and conflict conditions together to improve interventions that prevent child acute malnutrition. *Lancet Planetary Health* doi: [10.1016/S2542-5196\(21\)00197-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(21)00197-2)
- M.E. Brown**, C.W. Cooper, P. Griffith (2020) NASA's Carbon Monitoring System (CMS) and Arctic-Boreal Vulnerability Experiment (ABOVE) Social Network and Community of Practice. *Environmental Research Letters*. doi: [10.1088/1748-9326/aba300](https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aba300)
- Cooper, M., **M.E. Brown**, S. Hochrainer-Stigler, G. Pflug, I. McCallum, S. Fritz, J. Silva, A. Zvoleff (2019) Mapping the Effects of Drought on Child Stunting. *Proceeding of National Academy of Science*. 116 (35) 17219-17224; doi: [10.1073/pnas.1905228116](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1905228116)
- M.E. Brown**, V.M. Escobar (2019) NASA's Early Adopter Program Links Satellite Data to Decision Making. *Remote Sensing Journal*. 11:4, 406; doi: [10.3390/rs11040406](https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11040406)
- Iizumi T., M. Kotoku, P.C. West, J.S. Gerber, W. Kim and **M.E. Brown** (2018) Uncertainties of potentials and recent changes in global yields of major crops resulting from census- and satellite-based yield datasets at multiple resolutions. *PLoS One* 13: 9, e0203809. Doi: [10.1371/journal.pone.0203809](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0203809)
- M.E. Brown**, E.R. Carr, K. Grace, K. Wiebe, C. Funk, W. Attavanich, P. Backlund, L. Buja (2017) Do markets and trade help or hurt the global food system adapt to climate change? *Food Policy Journal*. In press. doi: 10.1016/j.foodpol.2017.02.004
- Davies D., **M.E. Brown**, K. Murphy, N. Stavros, B. Zavodsky, M. Carroll (2017) NASA Data for Time-Sensitive Applications: A Workshop Summary. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine*. Doi: 10.1109/MGRS.2017.2729278
- M.E. Brown**, Sabrina Delgado Arias, Thomas Neumann, Michael Jasinski, Pamela Posey, Greg Babonis, Nancy Glenn, Charon Birkett, Vanessa Escobar, Thorsten Markus (2016) Applications for ICESat-2 Data from NASA's Early Adopter Program. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine* 4(4) 24-37. Doi:10.1109/MGRS.2016.2560759
- M.E. Brown**, Monica Ihli, Oscar Hendrick, Sabrina Delgado-Arias, Vanessa M. Escobar, Peter Griffith (2015) Social Network and Content Analysis of the North American Carbon Program as a Scientific Community of Practice *Social Networks Journal*. 44: 22-237. doi:10.1016/j.socnet.2015. 10.002
- M.E. Brown** and C. Wooldridge (2015) Identifying and quantifying the benefits of meteorological satellites. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*. 97(1):182-185. doi:[10.1175/BAMS-D-14-00224.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-14-00224.1)

Walid Ouaret (Co-Investigator)

Department of Geographical Sciences
Interdisciplinary Sciences Bldg. 416, University of Montana, Missoula MT 59812
Phone: (513) 307-2675; wouaret@umd.edu

Education

Ph.D. (Currently) University of Maryland Geographical Sciences
M.S. (2017) AgroParisTech Climate, Land Use and Ecosystem Services
B.S. (2013) Ecole Nationale Supérieure Agronomique of Algiers Agronomy

Appointments

2021-Present Graduate Student Research Assistant, Department of Geographical Sciences,
University of Maryland
2018-2020 Assistant Research, Laboratory of Soil-Agrosystem-Hydrosystem Interaction,
Institute of Research and Development (IRD)
2017-2018 Guest Research Assistant, Plant Production System Group, Wageningen University
2014-2016 Research Assistant, Soil Science and Plant Diagnostics Laboratory, Mediterranean
Agronomic Institute of Chania

(i) Selected Publications Related to the Proposed Research

R. Hijbeek, M.P. van Loon, **W. Ouaret**, B. Boekelo, M.K. van Ittersum, Liming agricultural soils in Western Kenya: Can long-term economic and environmental benefits pay off short term investments?, *Agricultural Systems*, Volume 190, 2021, 103095, ISSN 0308-521X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2021.103095>.
Kherif, O.; Seghouani, M.; Zemmouri, B.; Bouhenache, A.; Keskes, M.I.; Yacer-Nazih, R.; **Ouaret, W.**; Latati, M. Understanding the Response of Wheat-Chickpea Intercropping to Nitrogen Fertilization Using Agro-Ecological Competitive Indices under Contrasting Pedoclimatic Conditions. *Agronomy* 2021, 11, 1225. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy11061225>
Kaci, G., **W. Ouaret**, and B. Rahmoune. "Wheat-Faba bean intercrops improve plant nutrition, yield, and availability of nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) in soil." (2022).

(ii) Other Significant Publications:

Ouaret, W., Salhi, Z., AitKaci, M., Ounane, S.M. Algerian Sourced Low-Cost Inorganic Sustainable Substrate For Soilless Cultivation. *1st Mediterranean forum: designing sustainable agricultural and production systems under global changes in the Mediterranean*. Montpellier, 2016.
Omar Kherif, Mohamed Islam Keskes, Marc Pansu, **Walid Ouaret**, Yacer-Nazih Rebouh, Peter Dokukin, Dmitry Kucher, Mourad Latati, Agroecological modeling of nitrogen and carbon transfers between decomposer micro-organisms, plant symbionts, soil and atmosphere in an intercropping system, *Ecological Modelling*, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2020.109390>.

4.2 Contributions of Key Personnel

Dr. Arthur Endsley (PI) is an NTSG research scientist at the University of Montana with expertise in Natural Resources and Scientific Computing. As PI, his responsibilities include communication and coordination with all project members as well as the overall responsibility for all project deliverables and periodic reporting to NASA. He will also co-lead the development of the curriculum along with Co-I Ouaret. He and Co-I Ouaret will share draft lesson plans and solicit feedback regularly from the Curriculum Advisory Committee (CAC). He will also leverage contacts in scientific software user communities (PyOpenSci, The Carpentries) to advertise the open curriculum, once published. PI Endsley will lead planning of the in-person teaching activities in Algeria with ENSA, with assistance from Co-I Ouaret. Endsley and Ouaret will jointly teach the final curriculum at ENSA in Year 2.

Dr. Molly Brown (Co-I) is a research professor at the University of Maryland in the Department of Geographical Sciences as well as the Chief Science Officer at 6th Grain, a private digital agriculture company. Co-I Brown will supervise Co-I Ouaret, a doctoral student, insofar as what is required for the student to remain in good standing. Co-I Brown will also serve on the Curriculum Advisory Committee (CAC) and provide continuous feedback on the curriculum as it is developed, particularly where her expertise in food security and remote sensing are needed.

Mr. Walid Ouaret (Co-I) will be a doctoral student at the University of Maryland in the Department of Geographical Sciences, starting in January 2023. As a project Co-I, he will collaborate closely with PI Endsley on the development of the curriculum: writing the narrative, researching example datasets, experimenting with candidate lesson materials, and testing code snippets. Co-I Ouaret will be responsible for the translation of final lesson materials into French and Arabic. Co-I Ouaret will directly translate materials into French and will coordinate and supervise the written Arabic translation provided by a contractor. Along with PI Endsley, Co-I Ouaret will co-teach the final draft curriculum in Algeria at ENSA, in Year 2. He will also help coordinate travel, on-site logistics, and networking with students, staff, and faculty in Algeria.

Dr. Mourad Latati (Collaborator) is a professor and researcher at ENSA in Algiers. He will lend his expertise in agroecological cropping systems and soil science to the Curriculum Advisory Committee. He will also help with logistics, curation of curriculum materials, and developing networking opportunities during the in-person workshops in Algeria.

Dr. Mohsen Nabil (Collaborator) is a remote sensing expert at the National Authority for Remote Sensing and Space Science, in the Agricultural Applications Department, Cairo, Egypt. He will lend his expertise in agricultural remote sensing to the Curriculum Advisory Committee.

4.5 Summary Table of Work Effort

The following table divides work effort by years, where the first column under (This Project) for each year (NASA Support) indicates the number of months committed to this project that will be directly funded by this proposal. The second column (Total) indicates the total number of months that will be committed to this project by the team member (including both time funded by this proposal AND to be supported by other means). This number should be greater than or equal to column one. The third column (Other Projects) indicates the number of months that are committed to other currently funded proposals (listed in “Current and Pending Support”). The three columns on the right (under Sum) are the total values for all years of the projects.

Name	Role	Commitment (months per year)					
		Year 1			Year 2		
		This Project		Other Projects	This Project		Other Projects
		NASA Support	Total		NASA Support	Total	
K. Arthur Endsley	PI	3.00	3.00	8.50	3.00	3.00	8.50
Molly F. Brown	Co-I	0.24	0.24	3.00	0.24	0.24	0.00
Walid Ouaret	Co-I	11.50	11.50	0.00	9.13	9.13	0.00
Sum of work effort (months):		14.74	14.74	11.50	12.37	12.37	8.50

4.6 Facilities and Equipment

4.6.1 University of Montana NTSG

Computing resources of the University of Montana Numerical Terradynamic Simulation Group (NTSG) will be used for any satellite and ancillary data processing in support of project objectives. NTSG compute facilities are routinely used for global processing and geospatial analyses of satellite remote sensing data supporting a broad suite of science applications. NTSG is a NASA Type II Earth Science Information Partner (ESIP-II), integrating biophysical theory, computational modeling and remote sensing for production, public distribution and support of a broad set of global satellite environmental data records, NASA Earth missions, and applications in partnership with NASA computing and data archive (DAAC) facilities.

NTSG compute facilities consist of a scalable Dell Nutanix hypervisor cluster and several standalone compute servers interconnected by a 10Gb Cisco switch and five Supermicro server blades networked to provide >100TB of high speed storage. These facilities aid in creation and management of two main compute Linux virtual machines (VMs) with 192GB RAM and 40 Xeon cores, three Linux dedicated VMs for services including authentication (LDAP), file routing between Linux and Windows, server maintenance, docker containers, and Windows servers for SQL databases and compute resources with 16GB RAM and 8 Xeon Cores. The Nutanix Servers include a Linux cluster of four blades, each with 32 Xeon processor cores and 256GB of memory; a baremetal cluster of five blades, each with 8 to 12 Xeon processor cores and 48GB to 64GB of memory.

Windows workstations include multi core AMD workstations with 8GB of Memory. Linux workstations include multi core Xeon workstations with 8-16GB of memory. Backup and storage hardware include a network of Synology NAS servers with 200TB storage capacity and three additional storage nodes each comprised of 100TB of storage. Software for these systems include: Compilers & Debuggers (C/C++, FORTRAN, Java, Python, perl), Networker, ENVI/IDL, Matlab, R, MS Office Pro, and ArcGIS. The University of Montana and NTSG also maintain a fast networking Internet-II (10Gb) connectivity link to remote sites and partners, including HPC facilities on NCCS Discover. The NTSG compute infrastructure was developed through previous and ongoing NASA Earth Science and mission support activities, and NSF funded Cyber infrastructure development awards to the UM.

4.6.2 University of Maryland

The Department of Geographical Sciences has excellent computing and network facilities in our research labs, which is equal to the best in the University. Currently our research environment has two High Performance Computing (HPC) clusters and two Hadoop Clusters, with internal high-speed networks within the clusters, among the clusters and public access to the clusters, and a tape library all focused on the department's research needs. Two HPC clusters are built on Redhat Enterprise Linux (RHEL) 7 operating system with direct access to storage via IBM

spectrum scale, a parallel file system which can handle multiple IO streams from each cluster node concurrently to the filesystem spanning multiple storage arrays.

The first HPC cluster is for the base research computing and shared by the entire department. It consists of 696 processing cores, 6.7 TB of Random-Access Memory (RAM) connected to backend online disk storage of 3.7 PB by multi-path redundant 8Gbps Fiber Channel (FC) network aggregated to 32Gbps using four FC switches per node. The department cluster utilizes a 10/25Gbps IP network. The second cluster was acquired exclusively for the Global Land Analysis & Discovery (GLAD) lab. It consists of 880 processor cores with combined RAM of 27.29 PB and connected to backend online disk storage of 25.32 PB. The GLAD cluster utilizes a 16Gbps Fiber Channel storage network with four paths that aggregate to 64Gbps per node. It utilizes a 40Gbps IP network for local and public traffic. The GLAD cluster would rank 10th in the world regarding total storage capacity hosted. The combined storage capacity of these two clusters is 29.02PB which brings the ranking down to 8th in the world of similar comparable research clusters. The HPC clusters are designed to scale, as needed with compute or storage by addition of modular units by PIs to meet the needs of their research grants. The HPC's can process large volumes (>1.5PB/day) of data with more efficient resource utilization than traditional HPC clusters, while scaling as needed.

Two Hadoop clusters run on the latest version of Cloudera. These provide a wide range of applications that can be tested using Big Data algorithms. The first Hadoop cluster consists of two named nodes with 14 processor cores, 256GB RAM, 2.4TB high performance storage and 32TB for data storage. There are 15 compute/data nodes with 300 processor cores (20 per system), 2.8TB RAM (192GB per system), 1TB for OS per system and 0.66PB (660TB) of HDFS storage for data storage (44TB per system). The second Hadoop cluster consists of one gateway node, three name nodes and 6 data/compute nodes. The gateway node has 20 processor cores, 256GB RAM, 64TB of data storage, providing storage space to stage pre-processing and post-processing data. The Department has large storage systems to meet the needs across the four clusters. The Department manages an IBM TS3500 tape storage library with three S53 expansion library modules with a total slot capacity of 4221 LTO tapes. Based on the compression that can be achieved on the data stored on the tape, the current capacity of the existing tapes is between 5.4 to 13.2PB with 5.4PB when no compression can be achieved during tape storage of the data to 100% compression achieved during tape storage.

The University of Maryland maintains a contract with all major public cloud providers AWS/GPC/Azure. UMD is an Internet2 member and has AWS Direct Connect. The research infrastructure is interconnected at 100Gbps to campus infrastructure and a 40Gbps backbone network and 1Gbps management network. This high-speed network enables faster data transfers with other academic and government agencies in the region through the 100Gbps MidAtlantic Crossroads network and beyond. The Department also supports a large inventory of client computing spanning Windows, Mac and Linux operating systems both in desktop/workstation and laptop class machines. The Department IT also supports Android and iOS-based handheld devices.

4.7 Letters of Support

(On following pages.)

REPUBLIQUE ALGERIENNE DEMOCRATIQUE ET POPULAIRE

وزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي
MINISTRE DE L'ENSEIGNEMENT
SUPERIEUR
ET DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE

المدرسة الوطنية العليا للفلاحة

ECOLE NATIONALE SUPURIEURE
AGRONOMIQUE

Pr. Latati Mourad
Department: Crop production
E-mail: m.latati@yahoo.com*
Tél: +213671606269
Higher National School of Agronomy (ENSA)
Street Hassan Badi, El Harrach, Algiers, Algeria

November 4, 2022

Dr. Endsley,

I acknowledge that I am identified by name as a Collaborator on the proposal titled “Satellite observations and models informing agriculture: Training for managers and researchers in a warmer and drier world,” that was submitted in response to the NASA Research Announcement NNH22ZDA001N-TOPST. I intend to carry out all of the responsibilities attributed to me in the proposal document. I understand that the extent and justification of my participation, as stated in the proposal, will be considered during peer review in determining the merits of the proposal. I have read the entire proposal, including the management plan and budget, and I agree that the proposal correctly describes my commitment to the proposed effort. To fulfill my responsibilities as part of this proposal, I will be working as a representative of the École Nationale Supérieure Agronomique of Algeria.

Sincerely,

Mourad Latati

Dr. LATATI Mourad
Maître de Conférence
Ecole Nationale Supérieure
Agronomique
ENSA - EL-HARRACH

NARSS

National Authority for Remote Sensing
& Space Sciences

November 4, 2022

Dear Dr. Endsley,

I acknowledge that I am identified by name as a Collaborator on the proposal titled “Satellite observations and models informing agriculture: Training for managers and researchers in a warmer and drier world,” that was submitted in response to the NASA Research Announcement NNH22ZDA001N-TOPST. I intend to carry out all of the responsibilities attributed to me in the proposal document. I understand that the extent and justification of my participation, as stated in the proposal, will be considered during peer review in determining the merits of the proposal. I have read the entire proposal, including the management plan and budget, and I agree that the proposal correctly describes my commitment to the proposed effort.

Sincerely,

Mohsen Nabil

Remote Sensing Expert (Ph. D),

Agricultural Applications Department

National Authority for Remote Sensing and Space Science

Cairo, Egypt. (mohsen.nabil@narss.sci.eg)

الجمهورية الجزائرية الديمقراطية الشعبية
République Algérienne Démocratique et Populaire
وزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي
Ministère de l'Enseignement Supérieur et de la Recherche Scientifique
المدرسة الوطنية العليا للفلاحة
Ecole Nationale Supérieure Agronomique

December 4, 2022

Dr. Endsley,

I am writing to express my support for your proposal, "Satellite observations and models informing agriculture: Training for managers and researchers in a warmer and drier world", in response to the NASA Research Announcement NNH22ZDA001N-TOPST. Your proposed activities will lead to a curriculum that is extremely relevant to the needs of our students and research staff and its translation into French will allow us to maintain and teach the curriculum in the following years. Should your proposal be funded, my institution will provide financial and in-kind support for the travel, lodging, and incidental costs associated with bringing yourself and Mr. Walid Ouret to Algeria for the purposes of teaching this curriculum.

Sincerely,

Directeur de l'Ecole Nationale
Supérieure Agronomique
Tarik
Professeur: **HARTANI Tarik**

